

Multi-axial stresses in intermittent rail welds

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ABSTRACT

For light to medium-heavy crane loads the rails are often attached to the crane runway by intermittent longitudinal rail welds. An intermittent rail weld offers advantages in many aspects and is often used in practice. For the fatigue verification though, only the detail of the intermittent weld between the flange and web of an I-section in Table 8.2, EN 1993-1-9 (1) can be used as a reference resulting in detail category 80 for longitudinal direct stresses in the flange. However, the shear stress is only considered indirectly, as described in (2). The transverse stresses from the wheel load, though, are not considered at all.

In the research project (2), this detail has been investigated experimentally and numerically. The results led to an amendment for the prEN1993-6 (3). Part of these investigations were fatigue experiments on 3.5 m long girders with intermittent rail welds. The rail welds were stressed in 6 four-point bending tests by longitudinal stresses only and in another 6 three-point bending tests with additional transverse stresses due to the wheel load. These tests had a stationary load, further 6 tests were run under a traveling load by the research partners at the Materials Testing Institute of the University of Stuttgart. The stationary experiments and the findings also in view of numerical studies are described and explained in this paper.

Keywords: wheel load, intermittent rail welds, crane runway beam, fatigue

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of intermittent rail welds (double fillet welds) to attach flat and square rail to the upper flange of crane girders has been a common method of construction for light to medium-heavy crane runway loads for many decades. The advantage of intermittent welds is aside of more easy fabrication the ability to verify the contact between rail and flange. This enables to ensure direct load transmission not only via the welds but also from rail to flange, which results in a more economical dimensioning of the welds. But the intermittent welds must be checked for fatigue due to the frequently recurring load. In Eurocode EN 1993-1-9 (1), however, this detail has been insufficiently covered so far, so that continuous rail welds are often used or the fatigue verification of the rail welds is avoided at all. The aim of the research project (2) was to close this gap and to define design guidelines for intermittent rail welds regarding fatigue. Some key questions had to be answered.

First of all, it had to be clarified which contact exists between the rail and the flange. Another question was the lack of a detail category classification for the stresses σ_{\perp} , σ_{\parallel} and τ_{\parallel} (see *Fig. 1*) and to what extent the various stresses affect the intermittent weld individually and in combination. For this purpose, 18 tests were carried out in three different test setups, as well as FE-analyses. The local transverse stresses σ_{\perp} , *Fig. 1a*) from the wheel load could be examined in the three-point bending test series B. To be able to better assess and differentiate the global longitudinal stresses also occurring there, four-point bending tests, series A were carried out, in which the welds were exposed to pure longitudinal stress σ_{\parallel} , *Fig. 1c*). The influence of the shear stress τ_{\parallel} , *Fig. 1b*) could then be examined

more closely, using FEA. A very important part of the research in (2) were additional tests with relative movement between the wheel load and the rail. The impact of the stresses due to the wheel load was significant, causing the welds to break along the weld, the crack initiating at the weld root. Based on them, nominal transverse stresses for the fatigue verification of intermittent rail welds were defined and an own detail category determined. Due to these findings, the stresses could be considered in a differentiated way, their interaction assessed and a detail category defined for the longitudinal stresses as well as for the transverse stresses.

Fig. 1.: Various cracks by various stresses (2)

The investigations on these questions led to an amendment (8), which covers the results and meanwhile has been integrated into the new version of Eurocode 3 for crane supporting structures prEN 1993-6 (3). In the following the focus is on the longitudinal stresses.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Contact between rail and flange

The contact between rail and flange was examined by Euler in (2), (4) and (5) using different approaches. This showed that a maximum gap width of 0,2 – 0,3 mm is possible to achieve a “technical contact” that enables load transfer directly between the rail and flange. Therefore, it is recommended to remove raised mill marks. The shape and position of mill imprints are particularly relevant. Elongated indentations near the weld can lead to increased stress on the weld and should therefore be avoided. Before attaching the rail, it should be double-straightened and fastened to the beam during the welding progress, e.g. using screw clamps (2), (4), (5).

2.2 Description of the experiments with stationary loading

Test specimens with the same dimensions and from the same manufacturer were used for all tests. The HEA 280 beams were 3.5 m long and a 3 m long rail with a profile of 50 x 30 mm was welded to the top in the middle. The material used for both was S355J2. The intermittent rails welds in chain weld configuration had a planned thickness of $a = 5$ mm, a length of $h = 50$ mm and a gap of $g = 250$ mm, resulting in a g/h ratio of 5. This is twice as large as specified in EN 1993-1-9 (1) for the detail on longitudinal flange stresses with intermittent welds, see Fig. 2, which, however can hardly be substantiated. On the other hand, the g/h ratio of 5 represents standard practice for typical runway beams.

Fig. 2.: EN 1993-1-9 (1) Table 8.2

The measured values of the weld thickness were in the mean 5.8 mm, the weld length on average 55 mm, which shortened the mean distance between the weld to 245 mm. In order to keep the gap between the rail and the beam as small as possible, the rails were clamped onto the beam during the

welding process, which was carried out alternately on both sides. However, due to the rolled skin on the beam and rail, an “ideal contact” could not be achieved.

Strain gauges were attached near the welds (local strains) and on the top and bottom of the beam (global strains) to improve observation of the crack development during the tests and later validation of the FE models. In the quasi-static preliminary tests, in which the load was gradually increased, these strain gauges showed a linear rise in the strains and good agreement with the strains calculated in advance. The cyclic tests were carried out with a constant stress amplitude and a ratio between the maximum and minimum stress of $R = 0.05$ at different load levels and with about 4.5 Hz. A more detailed description of the experiments can be found in (2) and (5).

2.3 Four-point bending tests – Series A

In these tests, as can be seen in Fig. 3 (Beam No. 7 to 12), the hinged roller bearings ① had a distance of 2.8 m. The load ⑤ was applied on the beam ② via a cylinder ③ and a calotte ④ simultaneously at a distance of 1 m using a traverse ⑥. To apply constant longitudinal tension to the six seams in the middle, the rail ⑦ was located on the underside of the beam.

Fig. 3.: Four-point bending test

As was to be expected with purely longitudinal stresses in the welds, the crack always started at the beginning or end of the weld. Crack growth was observed both in the rail and in the flange, as can also be seen in Fig. 4a). The failure criterion was the complete crack through the rail.

Fig. 4.: Cracks at the a) four-point bending tests b) three-point bending tests

The global longitudinal stresses at the level of the rail welds were calculated using the moment resulting from the loaded system and the section modulus determined individually on the basis of the measured geometry.

2.4 Three-point bending tests – Series B

In the test setup for this test series, also shown in *Fig. 5a*) (Beams No. 13 to 18), the rail ② was located at the top of the beam ①, the hinged roller bearings ③ were 1.8 m apart and the load was applied centrally by a stamp with a curvature of a diameter of 200 mm, modelled like a wheel ④. A more detailed view on this wheel can be seen in *Fig. 5b*). As with the four-point bending tests, the bending of the beam resulted in global longitudinal stresses.

Fig. 5.: Three-point bending test

The pressure of the wheel on the rail directly above the weld also resulted in additional local transverse stresses. Therefore, a crack parallel to the weld, starting from the weld root, was initially expected, as was also observed in the three-point bending tests under travelling load. However, it could be observed that here too, the cracks developed at the beginning and end of the weld, transverse to it, as shown in *Fig. 4b*). In all tests, the cracks grew from the weld toe into the flange. In three tests, secondary cracks were also observed transversely in the weld and in two tests at the weld toe into the rail. As the stressed area was in the compression zone, crack growth was significantly slower. It would therefore not have been practicable to define the failure criterion as crack through the flange. A crack length in the beam flange of 15 mm from the rail edge was therefore defined as the failure criterion. In addition, crack detection was more difficult and could only be done with fluorescent magnetic powder, whereby the test had to be stopped for a short time.

2.5 Test results

The number of cycles used in the evaluation refers to the failure criterion at the first weld transition. All other weld transitions, which are not taken into account here, therefore had a higher fatigue strength. Since 3 weld pairs were under maximum load in the four-point bending tests, 72 weld ends were tested with the 6 test specimens in series A. The sample size was therefore neglected in the further process.

Series A was evaluated first, as it had a clear failure criterion in terms of the fracture of the rail and had a wider distribution across the S/N-curve. The results of series A have a slope of $m = 3,07$ and a low standard deviation of only $S_n = 0,02$, which indicates standardized test conditions. This resulted in a fatigue strength of $\Delta\sigma_c = 115$ MPa. For series B with the failure criterion of a 15 mm long crack, an evaluation with a free slope was not suitable due to the low distribution over the S/N-curve. As with series A, fracture was also defined as failure criterion for an older test series by *Neumann* (6), which forms the basis for the detail category given in EN 1993-1-9 for the moment, but was on girder tests and not on the rail welded to the top flange. The standard deviation of $S_n = 0,148$ and the slope of $m = 4,11$ for these manually welded samples, on the other hand, is somewhat higher than series A, but results in a comparable fatigue strength of $\Delta\sigma_c = 111$ MPa, which is why these tests are evaluated together in the following. Tests from series A and from the test series by *Neumann* (6) of manual welded samples result in a fatigue strength of $\Delta\sigma_c = 101$ MPa for a fixed slope of $m = 3$. Adding the results of series B to this evaluation leads to the fatigue resistance $\Delta\sigma_c = 99$ MPa. The results can be seen in *Fig. 6* and are also represented in the amendment (7).

Fig. 6.: Evaluation of the test series A and B together with (7)

A further 6 three-point bending tests were carried out under travelling load. In these tests, the crack appeared from the weld root along the weld. More detailed description can be found in (2).

2.6 Further findings

Due to the manufacturing process, there were unintentional variations in the weld parameters, such as weld length, the offset of the opposing welds or the weld ends in relation to the applied load. The variations in the beams No. 13 – 18 covered the following range, seen in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Measured range of various parameters

	Weld length	Offset opposite weld ends	Offset weld - load
Min [mm]	56,0	0,0	20,0
Max [mm]	67,5	7,6	44,5

This allowed to investigate whether an influence on the fatigue strength could be seen within this range. The two maximum loaded seams per beam were compared. The distance between the load application and the end of the welds and the displacement of the opposing welds showed no significant influence on the appearance of the first crack or the crack length. However, it was found that the shorter weld was the first with a crack in all beams (8). This leads to conclusion that the fatigue strength improves with longer weld length.

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

3.1 Designing the model

The three-point bending test was modelled in Inventor (9) and calculated in Ansys Mechanical (10). The model of the beam was created according to the nominal dimensions of the HEA 280 beam, with a rail of 30 x 50 mm. The gap between the rail and the flange was 0.05 mm. The weld was modelled following the modelling of (11) with a transition radius of $r = 0.2$ mm. The weld thickness and length were based on the measured mean values of the tests. Finally, the weld was combined with the rail and the beam to form a single body, which enabled optimum meshing. The friction between wheel,

rail, beam and bearing was assumed $\mu = 0.2$. The materials of all parts were specified as structural steel (Young's Modulus $E = 200.000$ MPa). The bearing and the wheel were held in place, except the wheel could move in Z-axis to apply the load and the bearings could each rotate around the Y-axis. The global mesh of the beam was created with tetrahedrons with an edge length of 6 mm. A mesh of 1 mm length was created within a perimeter of 100 mm around the middle welds, which was reduced again to 0.5 mm at the weld ends, the weld transition was refined twice more. This was the result of a sensitivity analysis, which provided sufficiently accurate results for this mesh in a reasonable computing time. The load of 250 kN was applied to the upper surface of the wheel via an external point. For validation, the strains in X-direction along the beam, were compared with the measured strains of the tests. To confirm the global model, the strains were taken at the center of the underside of the beam and 30 cm from the load application point on the top of the rail, as well as at half the distance between the welds on both the flange and the rail. The measurements of the strain gauges, the FE model and the respective deviations in % can be seen in *Table 2*.

Table 2. Comparing mean values of strain gauges at the test specimens and FEA

Location	DMS [$\mu\text{m/m}$]	FEA [$\mu\text{m/m}$]	Deviation [%]	
Global:	Flange bottom	532	549	3.2
	Rail top	-290	-286	-1.4
	Between welds - flange	-257	-261	1.6
	Between welds - rail	-342	-351	2.6
Local	Flange	-718	-728	1.4
	Rail	-270	-53	19.6

Strain gauges were also attached to the flange and the rail directly next to the weld. The FE results deviate only slightly at the flange. At the rail next to the end of the weld however, the deviation is almost 20%. This is due to the steep gradient of elongation. It ranges from high tension directly at the weld transition to high compression only 10 mm further on. This can also be seen in the strain gauge measurements, where the results vary between $-246 \mu\text{m/m}$ and $-744 \mu\text{m/m}$, which leads to a mean value of $-270 \mu\text{m/m}$, despite being placed at almost the same location. The results were therefore considered sufficiently accurate and the model validated.

3.2 Stresses

As mentioned in the introduction, different stresses occur at the weld. The question therefore arose as to what degree these stresses might interact. The first indication was observed during the stationary tests. Although in series B, in contrast to series A, additional transverse stresses from the wheel load were applied to the welds, the longitudinal stress was decisive in both series A and B showing a comparable fatigue strength. A further indication of a possible superposition of the different stresses was provided by the comparison of the stationary tests and those with traveling load. Here, however, different locations of crack initiation were found in the two different test setups. In the longitudinal stress-dominated stationary tests, the crack was found to start at the weld toe *Fig. 7a/b*).

Fig. 7.: Crack initiation - stationary three-point bending tests a) and b) and maximum longitudinal stress in the FEA c)

In the tests with traveling load, which have a significantly higher shear (2) component, the crack initiation was at the weld root. This can also be observed in the FEA. The maximum longitudinal stresses in terms of magnitude, that is the highest compression, can be found at the weld toe to the flange, *Fig. 7c*). The maximum shear stress, seen in *Fig. 8* can be found in the weld root, in the tests *Fig. 8a*) as well as in the FEA *Fig. 8b*).

Fig. 8.: Crack initiation – a) at travelling load three-point bending tests and b) maximum shear stress in the FEA

Both the different failure locations and the different types of stresses in these different locations therefore indicate that the longitudinal stress at the weld toe and the shear stress at the weld root can be considered separately. An interaction of the stresses is therefore not necessary.

3.3 Parameter study

An experimental investigation of many parameters is hardly possible due to the cost-intensive tests. Therefore, various parameters were investigated in the FE model. Different weld lengths h with different weld distances g as well as various rail configurations were studied. The position of the load in relation to the weld was also changed. As the model was calculated without symmetry planes and was meshed for each geometry, there are slight variations in the mesh between the welds. Therefore, the maximum stresses of the two opposing middle welds were averaged.

– Variation of the weld length

The weld length has a positive effect on the longitudinal stress σ_{\parallel} at the weld end with increasing length, as can be seen in *Fig. 9a*). This is consistent with the findings from the experiments described in section 2.6, as there the shorter welds always showed the first crack. The higher stiffness of the beam and the resulting lower deflection of the beam with increasing weld length could also play a role here. The distance between the welds g does not play a significant part here. In contrast, the increasing weld distance g has a clearly negative effect on the shear stress in the weld root. As the weld length increases, not only global but also local stresses due to the prevented relative movement between the rail and flange have an influence with a negative effect on the fatigue strength of the weld root, as shown in *Fig. 9b*).

Fig. 9.: Influence of the weld length h at different distances g between the welds for the longitudinal stresses and the shear stresses

– *Rail configuration*

The wheel load can be distributed over a larger area due to both, an increased rail height and an increased rail width. This reduces the load on the welds and as a result, the stresses at the weld ends decrease. The stresses for a constant rail height can be observed in *Fig. 10a)* and *b)*, for a constant rail width the FEA results are shown in *Fig. 10c)* and *d)*.

Fig. 10.: Influence of the rail configurations for the longitudinal stresses and the shear stresses

– *Position of the wheel load*

In addition to the longitudinal stresses the transverse stresses from the wheel load were of interest for series B. As explained by *Euler (12)*, maximum shear stress and the transverse stress about the load application do not occur at the same position, as can be seen *Fig. 11*.

Fig. 11.: Stresses by direct load application (12)

If the transverse stress due to the load is decisive, the position of the load above the weld end leads to a maximum stress. If, on the other hand, the shear stress is decisive, the position above the weld midpoint leads to the highest stress. The stationary tests were carried out with the load above the weld midpoint, as it was assumed, that the shear stress would be decisive. In fact, the maximum shear stress occurs with the load over the midpoint of the weld.

The influence of the wheel load's offset from the weld midpoint, as it is explained in the figure in *Table 1*, was examined in this parameter study. The offset of 27.5 mm places the load exactly above the end of the weld. The results of the parameter study agree with *Euler (12)*. *Fig. 12b)* shows, that the maximum shear stress is at the midpoint of the weld. Also, the decrease of the stress with increasing offset can be seen in *Fig. 12b)*. The further the load moves away from the weld midpoint, the more the shear stress decreases. However, this behaviour is not evident for the longitudinal stress.

Fig. 12.: Influence of the wheel load position for the longitudinal stresses and the shear stresses

Fig. 12a) shows that the maximum longitudinal stress is not over the midpoint of the weld, but with an offset of 18 mm. But as mentioned, deviations in the position of the load application occurred up to 7.6 mm from the weld midpoint in the stationary tests, an effect which therefore is already considered in the results for the longitudinal stresses.

4 CONCLUSIONS

- *Interaction of stresses*
Series A without direct wheel load and series B with direct wheel load, both showed the same failure at the weld transition to the flange or the rail at the ends of the weld. The longitudinal stress was therefore decisive, irrespective of the transverse pressure caused by the wheel load. Also, the fatigue strength of the two series is comparable. This could also be observed in the FEA. The maximum stress in the longitudinal direction at the weld toe could be locally separated from the maximum shear stress in the weld root. An interaction of the shear stress with the longitudinal stress does not need to be considered.
- *Notch for the longitudinal stress*
Since no interaction between the shear stress and the longitudinal stress has to be considered, the statistically evaluated test results can be used to determine the detail category of the longitudinal stress with $\Delta\sigma_{||,c} = 90$ MPa. Therefore, for the verification of the longitudinal stress in the top flange underneath a rail welded with chain intermittent fillet welds with $l_w = 50$ mm, the detail category in EN 1993-1-9 Table 8.2 may be increased from 80 to 90.
- *Findings of the parameter study*
The parameter studies have shown that large rails in width and height have a positive effect on the stresses in the weld and therefore result in an increase in fatigue strength. Longer welds lead to lower longitudinal stresses, which could also be seen in the tests, but result in an increased shear stress. One observation is that the positioning of the load in the tests was not carried out at the most disadvantageous position with regard to the longitudinal stress. The measured deviations in the positioning of the load in the tests described in Table 1, as well as the reduction of the detail category of 10% from DC 99 to DC 90, may however cover an increase in the longitudinal stress by 9%.

Outlook

The results of the parameter study have shown that some factors have a positive influence on the fatigue strength. In order to be able to take these into account in design, further experimental studies focusing on the dimensions of the rail and the influence of the weld length and weld distance would be helpful.

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